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Reactive drug administration for reducing malaria transmission: A systematic review

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Reactive drug administration for reducing malaria transmission: A systematic review

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Table of contents

Table of Contents

Reactive drug administration for reducing malaria transmission: A systematic review	1
Background	4
Reactive drug administration.....	4
Objectives	4
Key question	4
Main objective	5
Secondary objectives	5
Methods.....	5
Criteria for considering studies for this review.....	5
Types of study included	5
Types of participants/population and setting.....	6
Types of interventions	6
Types of outcome measures.....	7
Additional data abstracted	7
Search methods for identification of studies.....	8
Databases.....	8
Reference lists.....	9
Other	9
Data collection	9
Selection of studies.....	9
Data extraction and management	9
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	10

Strategy for data synthesis	10
Main outcome measures	10
Specification of effect modifiers for subgroup analysis of subgroups or subsets	11
Contextual factors.....	11
Modeling studies.....	11
Grading certainty of the evidence	12
Results.....	12
Description of studies	12
Results of the search.....	12
Included studies	13
Interventions.....	15
Outcomes.....	15
Contextual factors.....	15
Excluded studies	16
Risk of bias in included studies	16
Effects of interventions.....	21
Incidence of parasitemia.....	21
Parasitemia prevalence.....	21
Confirmed malaria incidence	22
Adverse events.....	24
Other outcomes	24
Stratified comparisons	24
Contextual factors.....	24
Financial and economic costs	24
Acceptability.....	25
Feasibility	25
Mathematical modeling data.....	26
Discussion.....	26
References	27
References	41
Appendices.....	44
Appendix 1: Definitions of outcomes and contextual factors	44
Appendix 2: Search terms and results	46

Appendix 3: Alternative forest plots for prevalence of parasitemia and incidence of confirmed malaria
(with correct lower bound for 95% CI for Hsiang 2020(9))..... 48

Appendix 4: Detailed synthesis of contextual factors related to RDA..... 50

Background

Once malaria transmission declines to very low levels, case-based surveillance, namely reporting and investigating each passively-detected, parasitologically-confirmed malaria case (i.e. a symptomatic case presenting to a community health worker or a health facility), becomes feasible. Given the clustered nature of malaria cases at low transmission levels(1, 2), many countries pursuing malaria elimination have implemented strategies around parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases¹ in an effort to further reduce or interrupt transmission. Referred to as 'reactive' strategies, because they are initiated in response to confirmed cases, these actions may target both household members and neighbors of an index case, most commonly using reactive case detection (i.e. testing those around an index case for malaria and treating those positive with an antimalarial), reactive drug administration (i.e. administering an antimalarial to those around an index case without testing, regardless of symptoms), and reactive indoor residual spraying (IRS) of houses around an index case.

Reactive drug administration

Since current field-ready diagnostics are often not sensitive enough to detect low-density infections, which can be common in low-transmission settings(3, 4), reactive drug administration overcomes this potential barrier by treating those around an index case without testing. In addition, treating those around an index case, even if not currently infected with malaria, has a prophylactic effect that can contribute to reducing local transmission.(5) Modeling work supports the hypothesis that focal reactive drug administration will avert more cases than reactive case detection.(6) Empirical evidence in support of this strategy is still emerging, with several trials planned(5, 7, 8) and promising results available to date from only one completed high-quality study.(9)

Despite growing interest in strategies such as reactive drug administration and more countries implementing them, there has not been a systematic evaluation of the effectiveness of reactive drug administration.

Objectives

Key question

1. Should people residing with or near a confirmed malaria case be given a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication within one month of index case diagnosis to reduce human malaria transmission?

¹ There have also been studies that have conducted reactive strategies around cases identified through active surveillance. These studies will also be included in the review.

Main objective

1. To assess the benefits (on malaria transmission or burden) and harms (adverse effects) of treating adults and children residing in the same household or near parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases

Secondary objectives

1. To assess contextual factors, including values and preferences, resource use, impact on equity, feasibility, and acceptability of reactive drug administration.
2. To summarize findings from mathematical modeling studies with respect to the impact of various operational factors on the modeled efficacy of reactive drug administration, including size or population of the intervention area, the antimalarial medications used, and other relevant factors.

Methods

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of study included

Systematic review teams included studies that met eligibility criteria, regardless of language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, and in progress). For the main objectives, types of eligible studies included the following, listed in order of descending robustness):

- Randomized designs
 - Cluster randomized controlled trials (cRCTs) with: (a) the unit of randomization being a cluster, and (b) at least two clusters per arm.
 - Randomized cross-over trials with: (a) the unit of randomization being a cluster, and (b) at least two clusters per arm.
 - Stepped wedge design where clusters are randomly allocated, with at least four clusters
 - Factorial design with at least two clusters per level
- Non-randomized designs
 - Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials with at least two clusters per arm
 - Controlled before-and-after designs with (a) a contemporaneous control group, and (b) at least two clusters per arm.
 - Interrupted time series (ITS) studies (with or without a contemporaneous control group) with: (a) a clearly defined point in time when the intervention occurred, and (b) at least three data points collected before the start of the intervention and (c) at least three data points after the intervention that cover the same malaria transmission season as the pre-intervention data points and (d) balanced co-interventions before and after the start of the reactive intervention.

- Uncontrolled before-and-after studies (with a cluster design) or before-and-after studies with historical controls

Exclusion criteria included the following:

- Unit of randomization is at the individual level (for randomized trials)
- Unit of randomization is at the household level (for randomized trials)
- The intervention was administered to a subset of the population (i.e. based on age, occupation, etc.) in a defined geographic area
- Background malaria control interventions not evenly distributed/balanced across study arms
- Follow-up periods for intervention and control period not the same, or timing of baseline and endline surveys not at the same time in intervention and control
- Length of pre- and post-intervention periods for ITS studies are different (or cover different seasons)

For the secondary objectives (contextual factors and results from modeling studies), all study designs, including uncontrolled before-and-after studies, economic evaluations, qualitative studies, and other programmatic evaluations that include primary data, were considered.

Types of participants/population and setting

Adults and children of all ages living in areas with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential were included.

Types of interventions

Intervention arm

Reactive drug administration

Reactive drug administration consists of treating those living with or near an index case with a full therapeutic course of antimalarials.(9) This is done without screening (either for symptoms or parasites). There is no restriction on the type of antimalarial used as long as it is a therapeutic course. Treatment may also include an 8-aminoquinoline for radical treatment of hypnozoites of *Plasmodium vivax* and *P. ovale* index cases. Radical treatment was defined as a total dosage of 3.5–7 mg/kg of primaquine over 7 or 14 days or 8 weeks, depending on G6PD status, or as 300 mg of tafenoquine for those 16 years and older. The intervention must take place in a setting that offers adequate access to case management and the ability to do case-based surveillance, i.e., conduct an investigation of each confirmed case and report cases at the individual, versus aggregate, level. Most reactive drug administration efforts are based on passively detected index cases (e.g., at health facilities or by community health workers), but this intervention can also be in response to parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases identified through active case detection (e.g., household surveys).(10)

Comparator(s)/control

The comparators were no reactive drug administration (and could include another intervention, e.g., reactive case detection (RACD)). Studies with multiple intervention arms were included.

Background interventions

Both intervention and control arms should have the ability to do case-based surveillance. Vector control may or may not be in place in the intervention and comparison arms but should be implemented to the same degree in both arms.

Types of outcome measures

Studies were included if they reported at least one main outcome for inclusion in the main analysis. Additionally, any studies reporting original data on contextual factors were included in the synthesis of contextual factors, and any study reporting results (in terms of the main outcomes) from mathematical modeling were included in the synthesis of modeling results.

Main outcomes (see Appendix 1 for a summary of outcomes and contextual factors)

Measured at community level

- 1) Incidence of malaria infection
- 2) Prevalence of malaria infection
- 3) Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the peak transmission season)
- 4) Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases

Measured among those targeted by the intervention

- 5) Adverse events
- 6) Prevalence of infection

Additional data abstracted

Contextual factors

1. Values and preferences – The values and preferences of the individuals and populations affected by the recommendation with respect to the outcomes associated with the intervention;
2. Acceptability—Extent to which those benefiting from the intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention; includes willingness to participate in the intervention;
3. Health equity, equality and non-discrimination—Extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all;
4. Financial and economic considerations—Costs, resource intensiveness, overall economic impact, cost-effectiveness, cost-benefit;
5. Feasibility and health system considerations – legal barriers to implementation, interaction with existing health system, need for and use of the existing health workforce or other resources; programmatic considerations; timeliness (the ability to reach all targeted households/household members in a timely manner); adherence to drug completion among those given antimalarials; proportion of targeted population that is missed

Operational parameters

Insights from mathematical modeling on how variation in operational parameters alter the effectiveness of reactive drug administration were summarized for at least the following parameters, if available:

- Size or population of intervention area (e.g., radius) around the index case
- Antimalarial drug used

Potential effect modifiers

The potential effect modifiers specified in Table 1 were collected, when available, for each included study.

Table 1. Effect modifiers for RDA for sub-group analyses

Primary effect modifiers (pre-specified sub-group analysis)	Additional effect modifiers to be collected
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Level of transmission²• Vector control coverage• Malaria parasite species (Pf, Pv, Po or Pm) of index cases• Antimalarial medication used, including gametocytocide or hypnozoiticide• Size or population of intervention area (e.g., radius) around the confirmed case	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Whether all cases were included or only cases classified as local• Coverage of the intervention• Availability of G6PD screening (for Pv areas)• Rural vs. urban area

Search methods for identification of studies

We included all relevant studies regardless of date, language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, ongoing). Evidence was only included if publicly available (currently or by the time of publication of this review) or if provisions could be made to post information on a public website. In addition to studies evaluating the efficacy or effectiveness of RDA, we screened all papers from the search for studies with information on relevant contextual factors or on potential effect modifiers.

Databases

Studies were identified through comprehensive electronic database searches using study-specific search terms (Appendix 2) and the following databases: Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register; Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The Cochrane Library;

² The level of transmission was categorized according to the following schema found in the *Framework for malaria elimination*: High: incidence of about 450/1000 or Pf prevalence of $\geq 35\%$; Moderate: incidence of 250-450 per 1000 and Pf/Pv prevalence of 10-35%; Low: incidence of 100-250 per 1000 and Pf/Pv prevalence of 1-10%; Very low: incidence of < 100 per 1000 and Pf/Pv prevalence $< 1\%$.

MEDLINE (PubMed); EMBASE (OVID); and LILACS. We also searched Global Health; ProQuest Natural Science Collection; ZETOC; Tropical Diseases Bulletin; The Archives of the World Health Organization; US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (www.ClinicalTrials.gov/); ISRCTN registry (www.isrctn.com/); The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP) (www.who.int.ictrp).

Reference lists

Forward and backward citation tracking was done for the reference lists of all studies and articles identified by the above methods and screened at the full text screening stage.

Other

The following conference proceedings were reviewed for relevant abstracts: Seventh Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Dakar, Senegal; April 2018. Additionally, The Malaria Elimination Scientific Alliance assisted with conducting a 'Deep Dive' (<https://mesamalaria.org/mesa-track/deep-dives>) on RDA to identify planned and ongoing studies.

Data collection

Selection of studies

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts identified from literature and other searches; any potentially relevant articles identified by at least one reviewer were evaluated by the same two reviewers for full-text eligibility based on pre-determined inclusion criteria. At the full-text screening stage, two independent reviewers used a checklist to assess eligibility for inclusion, with discrepancies resolved by a third reviewer.

Data extraction and management

Two reviewers independently extracted information (at the full-text article stage) from studies on a pre-piloted electronic data extraction form. Prior to beginning full text data abstraction, a calibration exercise was conducted using the data abstraction form to ensure good concordance among reviewers. Any discrepancies were resolved by discussion to reach consensus or by consultation with a third reviewer. We contacted the original study author(s) when needed to retrieve any missing data or for clarifications.

The following information was extracted:

- **Setting:** Country, transmission intensity and seasonality, antimalarial drug resistance context, parasite species of interest
- **Participants:** Population characteristics, demographics
- **Study design:** Type; method of randomization (if applicable) and participant selection; adjustment for clustering (for cluster-RCTs); sample size; method of blinding of participants and personnel with respect to each outcome of interest.
- **Intervention/comparison:** Antimalarial(s) used; intended radius or number of households around index case; coverage (of intended households/household members), timing (average

time to intervention start after a confirmed index case); duration of intervention. Also, baseline coverage of malaria co-interventions in both intervention and control arms (if two-plus arms).

- **Outcomes:** Definition of outcome(s); diagnostic method or surveillance method for outcome measurement; population in which outcome was measured; number of events; number of participants or unit time; time point at which outcome was assessed in relation to start of intervention, statistical power; unit of analysis; incomplete outcomes or missing data; and results.
- **Contextual factors:** information on contextual factors (as defined under “Additional data abstracted”) was extracted from studies and summarized, but these data were not included in meta-analyses.

For dichotomous outcomes (e.g., prevalence), we extracted the number of prevalent cases (e.g., malaria infections) and number of participants (e.g., in a cross-sectional survey) in each study arm. For rate data (incidence), we extracted the number of events, the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm, and a measure of variance (standard error). For count data (number of indigenous malaria cases), we collected the number of events and the person-time or population over which they were reported. Where possible we used local cases only (as opposed to all cases) in the outcome, although this was possible for only one study (Vllakati 2021).

For cluster RCTs we recorded the number of clusters randomized; number of clusters analyzed; measures of effect (such as risk ratio, odds ratio, or rate ratios) with confidence intervals (CI) or standard deviations; number of participants (e.g., population in which the outcome was measured); and the intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC) value, if available. We abstracted the adjusted effect estimates, both adjusted for clustering (if appropriate) and adjusted for other relevant covariates, as reported by study authors and using models that were pre-specified in study protocols.

For non-randomized studies, we extracted adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempted to control for confounding, including risk ratios and rate ratios.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

Two members of the review team independently assessed the risk of bias for each included study using a tool designed to assess such risk on relevant domains as low risk, some concerns, or high risk and used summary graphs to display results. As the risk of bias in the effect of an intervention may be different for different outcomes, a ‘Risk of bias’ assessment for each outcome was made.

For each included RCT, the revised Cochrane ‘Risk of bias’ (ROB 2) tool(11) was used, along with other considerations in Chapter 8 of the Cochrane Handbook ‘Assessing risk of bias in a randomized trial’(12). Included RCTs were rated as low risk of bias, some concerns, or high risk of bias. We assessed non-randomized studies for risk of bias on standard criteria using slightly modified criteria from Table 2 in a recent publication on GRADE and risk of bias in non-randomized studies.(13)

Strategy for data synthesis

Main outcome measures

Measures of treatment effect

For study designs with a control group, the effect of the intervention was compared using risk ratios for dichotomous outcomes and rate ratios for rate, or counts, for example using Poisson regression or negative binomial analysis. For cluster-randomized trials, adjusted effect measures, both adjusted for clustering for other relevant covariates, as specified in the trial protocol and reported by study authors, constituted the primary measure of treatment effect. When possible, we performed sensitivity analyses using unadjusted (for other covariates) effect measures to investigate the robustness of our analyses.

Dealing with missing data

We attempted to contact study authors to obtain any missing data. No data imputation was applied.

Assessment of heterogeneity

For outcomes with more than one study contributing data, we assessed heterogeneity of main effects by examining forest plots for overlapping CIs. Statistical heterogeneity was examined using the I^2 statistic and classified according to the criteria below:

- Moderate: I^2 between 30% and 60%
- Substantial: I^2 values between 50% and 90%
- Considerable: I^2 values between 75% and 100%

If there was either considerable heterogeneity (I^2 statistic value between 75% to 100%) or inconsistency in the direction of the effect, or both, then we did not perform a meta-analysis. Clinical and methodologic explanations for heterogeneity were considered when I^2 indicates substantial heterogeneity (i.e., $I^2 > 50\%$).

Data synthesis

For outcomes with more than one study contributing data, we used fixed effects meta-analysis to combine data if heterogeneity was absent, when there were only two studies, or when there were data from multiple small but biased studies and one well-conducted study. Otherwise, we combined data using a random effects meta-analysis and reported a pooled treatment effect. Studies using uncontrolled before/after study designs were included in meta-analyses.

Specification of effect modifiers for subgroup analysis of subgroups or subsets

We attempted to stratify analyses of outcomes by potential effect modifiers (Table 1, above) if there were enough studies in each group.

Contextual factors

Information on contextual factors was grouped by contextual factor (from all study types) and presented in narrative summaries.

Modeling studies

Modeling studies were summarized in terms of their key findings with respect to likelihood of achieving outcomes and the effects of various model parameters. We assessed whether the model results supported or contradicted the findings from empirical studies.

Grading certainty of the evidence

Randomized trials (e.g. cluster RCTs, randomized cross-over trials, stepped wedge cluster randomized trials) started off with higher certainty than non-randomized studies (e.g. controlled before-and-after studies, ITS).

The certainty of evidence was evaluated using the GRADE approach(14) and each outcome was rated separately for evidence contributed by the randomized and non-randomized studies) as described by Balshem et. al.(15), using the GRADEPro software:

- High: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.
- Moderate: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect.
- Low: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited. The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
- Very low: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Randomized trials began as high-quality evidence but could be downgraded for valid reasons within the following five categories: risk of bias, imprecision, inconsistency, indirectness, and publication bias. Non-randomized studies began as low-certainty evidence but the certainty could be upgraded if there was a large effect, a dose response effect, and if all plausible residual confounding would reduce a demonstrated effect or would suggest a spurious effect if no effect was observed.(15)

Results

Description of studies

The included studies are described in more details in Table 4; the excluded studies are listed along with their reason for exclusion in [Table 3](#).

Results of the search

A total of 1,323 unique records were identified from the database searches, after one duplicate was excluded, and seven additional articles were identified from later full text screening. A total of 1,330 records were screened and 67 included for full text review. Of these, 53 were excluded for the reasons listed in **Figure 1** below, and the remaining articles had data abstracted for a total of six studies.

Figure 1: **PRISMA Diagram**

Included studies

Seven studies were included in the review for outcome data: six randomized trials and one non-randomized quasi-experimental study with a comparison group. Six studies were conducted in sub-Saharan Africa with nearly all infections due to *Plasmodium falciparum* and one study (Quispe 2018(16)) was conducted in Peru where malaria transmission was due almost entirely to *P. vivax*. In addition, one study using mathematical modeling (Gerardin 2016(17)) was identified. All studies except one (Eisele 2020—HIGH(18)) were from low-transmission settings; The Eisele 2020—HIGH(18) study took place in higher-transmission strata (*P. falciparum* prevalence of $\geq 10\%$) in Zambia (the other half of this trial that took place in low-transmission ($< 10\%$ PfPr) areas (Eisele 2020—LOW(18)) was considered as a separate study). Table 2 includes a summary of the included empirical studies; comprehensive details are provided in Table 4.

Table 2: Summary of included studies

Study	Country	Year(s) of study	Study design	Study arms	Comparison	Index case detection	Malaria species	Malaria transmission	Drug used	Outcomes included			
										Parasitemia incidence	Parasitemia prevalence	Confirmed malaria incidence	Adverse events
Bridges 2021	Zambia	2016–18	cRCT	2-arm trial comparing RDA with RACD	RACD	Passive surveillance	Pf	12.7 per 1,000 API in 2015	DP		X	X	X
Eisele 2020--LOW	Zambia	2015–16	cRCT	3-arm trial with two intervention arms (MDA and RDA) and one control arm	Control (no RDA)	Active surveillance (4 "rounds")	Pf	<10% PfPR among CU5	DP	X	X	X	
Eisele 2020--HIGH	Zambia	2015–16	cRCT	3-arm trial with two intervention arms (MDA and RDA) and one control arm	Control (no RDA)	Active surveillance (4 "rounds")	Pf	≥10% PfPR among CU5	DP	X	X	X	
Hsiang 2020	Namibia	2017	cRCT	4-arm trial with factorial design: RDA, reactive IRS (+RACD), RDA+reactive IRS, and RACD)	RACD	Passive surveillance	Pf	35.9 per 1,000 API in 2016	AL		X	X	X
Okebe 2021	The Gambia	2017–18	cRCT	2-arm trial comparing RDA with control*	Control (no RDA)*	Passive surveillance	Pf	4.6% and 8.4% parasite prevalence (by PCR) in 2012 in two study areas:	DP		X	X	X
Vilakati 2021	Eswatini	2016–17	cRCT	2-arm trial comparing RDA with RACD	RACD	Passive surveillance	Pf	6.3 per 1,000 API in RDA arm in 2012-2015	DP			X	X
Quispe 2018	Peru	2009–10	NRS	Comparison of districts with RDA versus districts with no RDA	Control (no RDA)	Passive surveillance	Pv	8.2 per 1,000 API in 2010	CQ+P Q			X	

cRCT=cluster randomized-controlled trial; MDA=mass drug administration; IRS=indoor residual spraying; Pf=*Plasmodium falciparum*; Pv=*Plasmodium vivax*; RACD= reactive case detection; NRS=non-randomized study; API=annual parasite incidence; DP=dihydroartemisinin-piperazine; AL=artemether-lumefantrine; CQ=chloroquine; PQ=primaquine.

* In the Okebe study, household members of the index case in the comparison arms were assessed for fever and tested if febrile; those positive were treated.

Interventions

In all studies except two (Eisele 2020(18)—LOW and Eisele 2020—HIGH(18)), RDA was conducted in response to a passively-detected case through the routine health system. In the Eisele 2020 trial, four rounds of active surveillance were done and cases identified by rapid diagnostic test (RDT) from the active surveillance triggered an RDA response.

In the studies from sub-Saharan Africa, the area around the index case targeted by RDA ranged from household members (Eisele 2020—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18)) or compound members only (Okebe 2021(19)) of the index case, to members of households within 140 meters (Bridges 2021(20)), 200 meters (Vilakati 2021(21)) or 500 meters (Hsiang 2020(22)) of the index case. All studies in sub-Saharan Africa except one in Namibia used standard treatment courses of dihydroartemisinin-piperazine (DP) for treating members of index and neighboring households; the Namibia study (Hsiang 2020(22)) used artemether-lumefantrine (AL) for treating household members and neighbors during RDA. The study from Peru (Quispe 2018(16)) used chloroquine (25 mg/kg for 72 hours) plus primaquine (0.5 mg/kg for 7 days) for treating household members (excluding children < 5 years, elderly members >65 years, pregnant women) and social contacts of index cases.

Three studies (Eisele 2020(18)—HIGH, Eisele 2020—LOW(18), and Hsiang 2020(22)) included additional intervention arms that were not included in this review: Eisele 2020(18)—HIGH, Eisele 2020—LOW(18) included a mass drug administration (MDA) arm and Hsiang 2020(22) used a factorial design with four arms: RDA, reactive IRS (plus RACD), RDA+reactive IRS, and RACD (considered the comparison). In the Namibia trial (Hsiang 2020(22)), we compared both RDA arms (with and without reactive IRS) to the RACD arm (with and without IRS). In two of the studies in sub-Saharan Africa (Eisele 2020(18)—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18)), RDA was compared to a control group that did not receive RDA. However, in three additional trials (Bridges 2021(20), Hsiang 2020(22), and Vilakati 2021(21)), RDA was compared to RACD using artemether-lumefantrine, which was supposed to be the standard of care; in the trial in The Gambia (Okebe 2021(19)), household members of the index case in the comparison arm were assessed for fever and tested if febrile; those testing positive were treated with artemether-lumefantrine. All studies with RACD as the comparison arm using artemether-lumefantrine (AL) to treat those testing positive during RACD.

Outcomes

Two studies (Eisele 2020—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18)) reported parasitemia incidence using data from a cohort of individuals in each study arm. Five studies (Bridges 2021(20), Eisele 2020—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18), Hsiang 2020(22) and Okebe 2021(19)) reported on parasitemia prevalence through cross-sectional surveys after RDA implementation. All seven studies reported on the outcome of confirmed malaria incidence using routine health system data. Four studies (Bridges 2021(20), Hsiang 2020(22), Okebe 2021(19) and Vilakati 2021(21)) reported on adverse events (AEs) but all except one (Hsiang 2020(22)) reported AEs only from the RDA arm.

Contextual factors

Five of the included studies in sub-Saharan Africa (Eisele 2020—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18), Hsiang 2020(22), Okebe 2021(19) and Vilakati 2021(21)) had associated publications reporting on contextual factors, including acceptability (n=6 publications), feasibility (n=7 publications), and cost (1 publication).

Excluded studies

Table 3: List of excluded studies

[TO COME]

Risk of bias in included studies

Risk of bias is summarized separately for randomized and non-randomized studies below.

Randomized studies

Assessments for risk of bias for each study are summarized in **Figure 2** and **Figure 3** with additional details behind these judgements provided in the Table 4: Characteristics of included studies.

Randomization process

Five of the six studies (all except Vilakati 2021(21)) were rated as low risk of bias in terms of the randomization process. All studies used acceptable randomization methods, such as computer-generated randomization or picking clusters from a hat (Bridges 2021(20)). The Vilakati 2021(21) study was rated as ‘Some concerns’ given large imbalances in malaria incidence at baseline, resulting from inclusion only of clusters that had an incident case during the RDA period.

Recruitment of participants into clusters

Risk of bias for recruitment of participants into clusters was rated as low for five of the six cluster-randomized trials. For the Bridges 2021(20) trial in Zambia, the study authors speculated that there was a higher refusal rate in the RDA arm (compared to the RACD arm), and risk was therefore rated as ‘Some concerns’.

Deviations from intended interventions

In five of six studies, there were no notable deviations from the intended interventions except for the Eswatini study (Vilakati 2021(21)), where 20 RACD interventions were delivered in RDA arm (14 clusters) and 5 RDA interventions delivered in RACD arm through mix-ups; this study was rated as ‘Some concerns’ for risk of bias this domain.

Missing outcome data (for each outcome)

For the two studies reporting on parasitemia incidence (Eisele 2020—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18)), the rating for this domain was low-risk. The mean monthly follow-up similar across study arms, and nearly 90% of participants in the cohorts contributing to this outcome completed % completed at least 12 months of follow-up.

For parasitemia prevalence, all four studies were rated as low bias. Data were collected through cross-sectional surveys, and there were no indications of differential missingness by study arm or high rates of missingness overall.

For the outcome of confirmed malaria incidence, all six studies contributing to this were rated as low risk. This outcome was reported through routine health system data in all relevant studies, and although not every study reported on the completeness or other quality aspects of routine data, it is unlikely that

there were differential missingness or quality concerns by study arm, given the randomized nature of these studies.

For the outcome of adverse events, three of the four studies (Bridges 2021(20), Okebe 2021(19)), and (Vilakati 2021(21)) were rated as high risk of bias for measurement of outcome. In these studies, there was no mention of adverse events being captured in the non-RDA arm. The Namibia trial (Hsiang 2020(22)) was rated as some concerns as one adverse event was reported from the RACD arm, although it is likely that the focus on adverse event reporting was much stronger in the RDA arm.

Measurement of outcome (for each outcome)

For parasitemia incidence, the two included studies (Eisele 2020—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18)), were rated as low risk; measurement of the outcome was done by PCR, and even in the absence of explicit blinding, it is highly unlikely that laboratory staff knew the study arm of the patient and potentially altered the outcome as a result.

For parasitemia prevalence, all four included studies were rated as low risk of bias. In all studies this outcome was measured in cross-sectional surveys by RDT in the field (Eisele 2020—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18)), or by PCR (Hsiang 2020(22) and Okebe 2021(19)) conducted at a later time point in the laboratory. For both diagnostics, we deemed it highly unlikely that study or laboratory staff would deliberately change their interpretation of these relatively objective diagnostic tests based on knowledge of study arm.

For confirmed malaria incidence, all but one study was rated as low risk, given that it is unlikely that clinicians at health centers would know which study arm the patient is from and use that knowledge to alter their diagnostic or treatment practices. One study in The Gambia (Okebe 2021(19)) was rated as some concerns, given that the Village Health Workers diagnosing and treating patients coming with fever were the same health workers carrying out RDA.

For the outcome of adverse events, all four studies were rated as high risk of bias. Studies typically had much more proactive approaches to detecting adverse events (such as follow-up visits to households receiving RDA) in the RDA arm compared to the RACD or comparison arm.

Selection of reported result (for each outcome)

All outcomes were pre-specified. For adverse events, all studies contributing to the outcome were rated as low risk of bias as it was a pre-specified outcome reported as simple numbers and percentages. In some cases for the malaria reduction outcomes, the specific covariates for adjustment of the outcome effect were not pre-specified; we considered this reasonable if the published protocol allowed for adjustment of baseline imbalances or a certain types of covariates. One of the Zambia trials (Bridges 2021(20)) was rated as 'some concerns' for the outcome of confirmed malaria incidence. The published protocol only stated that environmental variables would be adjusted for, but the results also included adjustment for previous month's cases and RDTs done.

Figure 2: Risk of bias summary for randomized studies: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for each included study

	Randomization process	Recruitment of participants into clusters	Deviations from intended interventions	Missing outcome data: Parasitemia incidence	Missing outcome data: Parasitemia prevalence	Missing outcome data: Confirmed malaria incidence	Missing outcome data: Adverse events	Measurement of outcome: Parasitemia incidence	Measurement of outcome: Parasitemia prevalence	Measurement of outcome: Confirmed malaria incidence	Measurement of outcome: Adverse events	Selection of reported result: Parasitemia incidence	Selection of reported result: Parasitemia prevalence	Selection of reported result: Confirmed malaria incidence	Selection of reported result: Adverse events
Bridges 2021	+	?	+			+	-			+	-	+		?	+
Eisele 2020-HIGH	+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+		+	+	+	
Eisele 2020-LOW	+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+		+	+	+	
Hsiang 2020	+	+	+		+	+	?		+	+	-		+	+	+
Okebe 2021	+	+	+		+	+	-		+	?	-		+	+	+
Vilakati 2021	?	+	?			+	-			+	-			+	+

Note: 'Unclear risk of bias' should be interpreted as 'Some concerns'.

Figure 3: Risk of bias graph for randomized studies: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies

Note: 'Unclear risk of bias' should be interpreted as 'Some concerns'.

Non-randomized studies

Only one non-randomized study (Quispe 2018(16)) was included and provided data for one outcome (confirmed malaria incidence). The review authors rated this study as having 'Some concerns' for four of the five risk of bias domains assessed for non-randomized studies. Regarding appropriate eligibility criteria, although there was a comparison district included, there were substantially lower rates of malaria incidence at baseline in these districts compared to those receiving RDA, raising some questions about the appropriateness of this comparison. For measurement of the exposure, no information was given on the proportion of index cases in the RDA districts that were followed up, and on the numbers of people receiving treatment around the index case. Regarding measurement of the outcome, no information was given on the quality or missingness of data in the routine system; given that the RDA districts were purposefully selected and had high malaria incidence at baseline than the comparison districts, we rated this as 'Some concerns'. We also rated control of confounding as 'Some concerns' given that baseline measures of malaria incidence in the study districts did not appear to be explicitly accounted for in the study regression model. Finally, we rated follow-up as 'Low-risk' as there is no

plausible reason to expect differential loss of routine data in the intervention versus control arm during the two years of the study. Given the non-randomized nature of the study, that four of five risk of bias domains for this study were rated as ‘Some concerns’, the Quispe 2018(16) study was judged to be at high risk of bias overall.

Figure 4: Risk of bias summary for non-randomized study: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for included study

Note: ‘Unclear risk of bias’ should be interpreted as ‘Some concerns’.

Figure 5: Risk of bias graph for non-randomized study: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies

Note: ‘Unclear risk of bias’ should be interpreted as ‘Some concerns’.

Effects of interventions

Incidence of parasitemia

Two studies (Eisele 2020—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18)) in Zambia reported data on parasitemia prevalence using cohorts of individuals in the RDA and the control arms. Neither the high-transmission or the low-transmission study indicated a significant reduction in parasitemia incidence, although the study in the low-transmission areas indicated a non-significant 34% reduction in parasitemia incidence (rate ratio 0.66, 95% CI: 0.30, 1.48) (Figure 6). The pooled estimate of the two trials indicated a non-significant reduction in parasitemia incidence (rate ratio: 0.73, 0.36, 1.47).

Figure 6. Forest plot of comparison: RDA versus no RDA/RACD on incidence of parasitemia

Footnotes

- (1) and (2) Negative binomial regression with random effect (cluster level) and adjusted for first month incidence, age, gender, household SES, vector control, rainfall, EVI, and elevation

Parasitemia prevalence

Four studies reported on parasitemia prevalence after RDA. The high (Eisele 2020—HIGH(18)) and low-transmission (Eisele 2020—LOW(18)) trials in Zambia found no reduction in parasitemia prevalence, adjusting for other factors, after RDA targeting index case households identified through four “rounds” of active surveillance. For the Namibia trial (Hsiang 2020(22)), we abstracted data from the analysis model that was pre-specified in the study protocol (adjustment for baseline imbalances only); this result showed a non-significant reduction in parasitemia after RDA (odds ratio = 0.54 (95% CI: 0.05, 1.04), adjusted for baseline malaria incidence (both with and without reactive IRS), compared to RACD (both with and without reactive IRS). The authors calculated the effect size using marginal effects post-estimation (to account for reactive IRS in half the clusters) after a regression model, thus the 95% confidence interval (CI) bounds are not balanced around the point estimate; as the Review Manager software can only accommodate balanced CIs, the 95% CI in Figure 7 contains the correct upper bound but is artificially narrow. A sensitivity analysis with the correct lower bound (but an artificially wide CI) is provided in Appendix 3. The trial in The Gambia (Okebe 2021(19)) found a non-significant reduction, adjusting for other factors, in parasitemia prevalence after RDA: odds ratio = 0.71 (95% CI: 0.27, 1.84). The pooled estimate across the four trials indicated a non-significant reduction of RDA on parasitemia prevalence: pooled odds ratio = 0.78 (95% CI: 0.52, 1.17).

Figure 7: Forest plot of comparison: RDA versus no RDA/RACD on parasitemia prevalence

Footnotes

- (1) and (2) Random effects logistic regression model adjusted for child age (in years), gender, household wealth from an asset index, rainfall, enhanced vegetation index, household elevation, and household protection by LLINs and IRS.
- (3) The 95% CI lower limit is higher here than in the published paper (odds ratio = 0.54, 95% CI: **0.05**, 1.04). Effect size from (non-linear) marginal effect post-estimation from generalized estimating equations (GEE) model using a logit function with variables for RDA, reactive IRS, the interaction between reactive IRS and RDA, and adjusted for 2016 incidence of local cases. Unadjusted effect size (from post-estimation marginal effect of RDA from GEE model using a logit function with variables for RDA, reactive IRS, the interaction between reactive IRS and RDA but no other covariates): 1.05 (0.03, 2.07).
- (4) Random effects logistic regression (random effect for health facility) adjusted for age. Unadjusted odds ratio: 0.73 (95% CI: 0.27, 1.94).

Confirmed malaria incidence

Randomized studies

All six randomized trials reported on the outcome of confirmed malaria incidence during RDA implementation. The Bridges 2021(20) trial from Zambia found a non-significant reduction, adjusting for other factors, in confirmed malaria case incidence during RDA: rate ratio = 0.80 (95% CI: 0.49, 1.30). The two other trials from Zambia (Eisele 2020—HIGH and Eisele 2020—LOW(18)) found no effect of RDA on confirmed malaria incidence, adjusting for other factors: rate ratios of 1.03 (95% CI: 0.84, 1.27) and 0.96 (95% CI: 0.77, 1.20), respectively. For the Namibia (Hsiang 2020(22)), we abstracted data from the analysis model that was pre-specified in the study protocol (adjustment for baseline imbalances only); the results showed a non-significant reduction of RDA on confirmed malaria incidence, adjusting for 2016 case incidence: rate ratio = 0.71 (95% CI: 0.22, 1.20). The authors calculated the effect size using marginal effects post-estimation (to account for reactive IRS in half the clusters) after a regression model, thus the 95% confidence interval (CI) bounds are not balanced around the point estimate; as the Review Manager software can only accommodate balanced CIs, the 95% CI in Figure 8 contains the correct upper bound but is artificially narrow. A sensitivity analysis with the correct lower bound (but an artificially wide CI) is provided in Appendix 3.

The trial in The Gambia (Okebe 2021(19)) found a non-significant reduction in confirmed malaria incidence, adjusting for other factors (rate ratio = 0.81, 95% CI: 0.59, 1.11), as did the trial in Eswatini (Vilakati 2021(21)) (rate ratio = 0.82, 95% CI: 0.39, 1.71). The pooled estimated across the six trials showed a non-significant reduction in confirmed malaria incidence, adjusting for other factors, from RDA: pooled rate ratio = 0.93 (95% CI: 0.82, 1.05).

Figure 8: Forest plot of comparison: RDA versus no RDA/RACD on confirmed malaria incidence

Footnotes

- (1) Negative binomial analysis of monthly facility cases (random intercept for facility); adjusted for previous month's cases, normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), precipitation, altitude, night-time light, number RDTs done each month, and seasonality (fourier term). Unadjusted estimate: 1.08 (95% CI: 0.78, 1.49).
- (2) and (3) Negative binomial difference-in-differences model (one pre- and one post time point), adjusted for prior month's cases, calendar month, rainfall, and EVI monthly anomalies.
- (4) The 95% CI lower limit is higher here than in the published paper (rate ratio=0.71 (95% CI: **0.22**, 1.20). Effect size from (non-linear) marginal effect post-estimation from a negative binomial model with offset for cluster-level person time; variables for RDA, reactive vector control, interaction between RDA and reactive vector control, and adjusted for 2016 incidence of local cases. Unadjusted marginal effects from post-estimation (from unadjusted negative binomial model with terms for RACD, reactive IRS, and the interaction between the two, with offset for cluster-level person time): 0.82 (0.26, 1.37).
- (5) Poisson regression model adjusted for age. Unadjusted estimate from a logistic regression model (with a random effect for cluster): 1.04 (95% CI: 0.57, 1.91).
- (6) Negative binomial regression model of local cases with offset for person-time and adjusted for baseline (2014-2015) incidence of local cases. Unadjusted estimate: 1.06 (95% CI: 0.57, 1.98).

Non-randomized studies

One non-randomized study (Quispe 2018) used a time-series analysis of routine health facility data to report on confirmed malaria incidence from two RDA districts and 8 districts not implementing RDA over two years in Tumbes, Peru. Using a mixed-effects Poisson regression model and controlling for several environmental variables, the authors found a rate ratio of 0.59 (95% CI: 0.40, 0.86) for the effect of RDA.

Figure 9: Forest plot of comparison: RDA versus no RDA/RACD on confirmed malaria incidence for non-randomized studies

Adverse events

Four randomized trials reported on adverse events (AEs); however, AEs were typically only actively solicited from the RDA arm and not from the comparison or RACD arm. In the Zambia trial comparing RDA using dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) with RACD using artemether-lumefantrine (AL), 123 (6.9%) mild AEs occurred in 1,775 people treated with DP (Bridges 2021); all resolved. In the Namibia trial (Hsiang 2020) of RDA with AL compared to RACD with AL, 17 of 4,247 treated participants (0.4%) in the RDA arm experienced an AE versus 1 participant of 96 (1.0%) treated in the RACD arm; 11 AEs were considered unrelated, 6 possibly related, and 6 probably related. In The Gambia (Okebe 2021), 75 AEs (7.6%) among 979 participants receiving DP in the RDA arm reported AEs; 69 were considered mild and 6 moderate. In Eswati, 68 (3.8%) of 1,776 participants receiving RDA with DP experienced AEs; 54 were rated as mild and 14 as moderate.

Other outcomes

There were no studies that reported data on the outcome of elimination or on parasitemia prevalence among those receiving RDA.

Stratified comparisons

Since only one study (Eisele 2020) reported data from a setting with moderate malaria prevalence (*P. falciparum* $\geq 10\%$ in half the study clusters), and the rest of the studies were from settings with low or very low malaria prevalence (*P. falciparum* prevalence $< 10\%$), we were not able to stratify results by transmission setting. Similarly, there was only one non-randomized study (Quispe 2018) conducted in a setting with predominantly *P. vivax* malaria transmission, and therefore we were not able to stratify results by malaria species.

Contextual factors

Financial and economic costs

Data on financial and economic costs of RDA were abstracted from a cost-effectiveness publication(23) linked to two studies conducted in Zambia (Eisele 2020(18)—LOW and Eisele 2020—HIGH(18)). The total cost of two rounds of RDA (with DP) conducted between 2014 and 2015 that covered a total population of 132,393 was US \$912,767 (all figures in 2015 US\$). The mean cost per person treated per health facility catchment area was \$85.69 (IQR \$39.92). The overall incremental cost per infection and case averted (vs. standard of care) for RDA was \$810 and \$6,353, respectively. In high-transmission settings, the incremental cost per infection and case averted were \$429 and \$5,951 respectively; and in low-transmission settings it was \$1,119 and \$6,755, respectively. Incremental cost per DALY averted for infections and cases were \$4,889 and \$38,344 respectively.

The cost-effectiveness study(23) reported that RDA does not appear likely to achieve WHO thresholds for being considered a “cost-effective” or “highly cost-effective” intervention. Results of this study showed similar costs of RDA and mass drug administration (MDA) per person targeted and reached (US\$9.01 versus US\$8.49 per person, respectively, $P = 0.87$). However, MDA was reported to be superior in all cost-effectiveness measures, including cost per infection averted (\$354 for MDA vs. \$810 for RDA),

cost per case averted (\$1,872 vs. \$6,353) and cost per disability-adjusted life year (DALY) averted for infections (\$2,137 vs. \$4,889) and cases (\$11,299 vs. \$38,344).

Acceptability

RDA community acceptability data were abstracted from publications associated with five studies from Eswatini (Vilakati 2021(21)), The Gambia (Okebe 2021(19)), Namibia (Hsiang 2020(22)), and Zambia (Eisele 2020(18)—LOW and Eisele 2020—HIGH(18)). Community acceptance of RDA was high (refusal rate of 2% or lower) in Namibia and Zambia(9, 24). However, in Eswatini, the overall refusal rate was about 4% with refusal rate of 1.4% (11/776) and 5.3% (65/1232) in seasons 1 and 2, respectively. In Zambia, there was a large increase in the self-reported acceptability of prophylactic treatment after testing negative for malaria from the baseline to follow-up survey for adults and children, from 62% to 96%(25). Intensive community-wide sensitization program that occurred before the first treatment round at each household during community health worker visits is reported to have resulted in this increase. Despite low refusal rates, stigma associated with malaria RDTs, Community Health Care Workers (CHWs), and treatment were reported in some of these countries. In Zambia, participants were concerned “whether CHWs or the program was tenets of Satanism” and said “this medicine you have brought is Satanic” (25). In Namibia, participants expressed concern about having “to take medicine without feeling sick” (26). Similarly participants in The Gambia “generally considered it unnecessary to take medication without having any symptoms” (27). Continued community sensitization has been recommended to mitigate these stigmas. In our review, we found no study reporting on health care workers’ or policymakers’ acceptability of RDA.

Feasibility

Data on feasibility of implementing RDA were abstracted from publications associated with four studies from Eswatini, The Gambia, Namibia, and Zambia. All countries used a three-day regimen of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) for RDA, except Namibia, where a three day regimen of AL was used. RDA coverage, defined as the proportion of index cases followed up, varied between countries with a low of 62.4% for index case coverage in Eswatini to about 97% in The Gambia.

RDA adherence data were abstracted from 3 studies from Eswatini, The Gambia, and Zambia. Full adherence, defined as taking all three doses of DP and verifying that no tablets were remaining in the blister pack was above 90% in all the countries. DP was generally reported to be well tolerated with mild to moderate self-limiting side effects. However, a study from Zambia reported that 5% of patients receiving DP stopped treatment early due to unspecified side effects(28). In Zambia, factors positively related to DP adherence were RDT positivity, age >15 (versus <5 years), receiving the first dose as directly-observed therapy (DOT) by the community health worker (CHW), and hearing sensitization messages; one factor negatively related to adherence was fever in last 2 weeks (28). In a study from Namibia, respondents anticipated reluctance about completing the full course DP, explaining that some people might stop once symptoms diminished, or if symptoms did not subside immediately. Respondents also reported that “people may save medication to treat future illness, given limited access and distance from health facilities” (26).

Mathematical modeling data

One study (Gerardin 2016(17)) was identified that provided modeling insights into the effect of RDA on the potential for malaria elimination. The study used data from Zambia in an agent-based model of malaria transmission and immunity acquisition (EMOD DTK v2.0) to assess the effect of various drug-based strategies for interrupting malaria transmission. In various simulations, the authors found that using RDA (treating households within 200 meters of a passively detected case by RDA) was unlikely to result in interruption of transmission (although at higher coverage levels MDA or RDA based on households identified through serological diagnostics are likely to contribute to elimination). In terms of reducing transmission, the authors found that at higher malaria prevalence and higher intervention coverage, RDA strategies were just as effective as MDA at reducing onward transmission.

Discussion

[To come pending GDG discussion]

References

Table 4: Description of included studies

Randomized studies

Bridges 2021

Methods	<p>Location: Southern Province, Zambia</p> <p>Study dates: May 2016 – May 2018</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: ~3 per 1,000</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial</p> <p>Unit of randomization: Health facility catchment area</p> <p>Total number of clusters (total): 16</p> <p>Clusters in RDA arm: 8</p> <p>Total population in RDA arm: ~63,000</p> <p>Total population in control/comparison arm: ~56,000</p>
Participants	<p>Number of RDA ‘events’: 302</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 1,775</p> <p>Percent of total targeted: 95.2% (1,775/1,865)</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RDA: Dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine</p> <p>Index case detection: Through passive surveillance at health facilities and CHWs</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: 140 meters</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Reactive case detection with artemether-lumefantrine and a 140-meter radius</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> ITNs, IRS, good malaria case management</p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Prevalence of parasitemia:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional household survey</p> <p>Persons sampled: Children aged ≥1 month to <15 years</p> <p>Diagnostic test used: PCR</p> <p>Time point(s): One time post-intervention (April–May 2018)</p> <p>Sample size: 3,151 (RDA), 3,125 (RACD)</p> <p><u>Incidence of clinical cases:</u></p>

	<p>Measurement: Weekly and monthly routine data on malaria cases (clinical and laboratory-confirmed) from community health workers and facilities accessed through DHIS2</p> <p>Time points: May 2016 – May 2018</p> <p><u>Adverse events:</u></p> <p>Dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine used in RDA arm; artemether-lumefantrine used in RACD arm. 123 reported only in RDA arm: headache (20%), abdominal pain (17%), dizziness (17%), or nausea (16%). All were mild and self-resolved.</p>
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Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Randomization process	Low risk	Clusters were picked from a hat.
Recruitment of participants into clusters	Some concerns	Authors speculated there was a higher refusal rate in RDA arm.
Deviations from intended interventions	Low risk	No evidence that incorrect interventions delivered.
Missing outcome data (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Authors reported no missing routine data (per correspondence)
Missing outcome data (adverse events)	High risk	Adverse events reported only in RDA arm
Measurement of outcome (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Data collected at health facilities and by CHWs for clinical management.
Measurement of outcome (adverse events)	High risk	Unclear whether adverse events reported from non-RDA arm
Selection of reported result (clinical malaria incidence)	Some concerns	Although outcome was pre-specified, the pre-specified model in the published protocol only mentioned adjustment for environmental variables, but not for previous month's cases and RDTs done, which were both included.
Selection of reported result (adverse events)	Low risk	Standard adverse events reported.

Eisele 2020-LOW and Eisele 2020-HIGH

Methods	<p>Location: Southern Province, Zambia</p> <p>Study dates: May 2014 – May 2016</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: N/A; half clusters in higher prevalence ($\geq 10\%$ PfPr) areas; half clusters in lower prevalence ($< 10\%$ PfPr) areas</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial</p>
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	<p>Unit of randomization: Health facility catchment area</p> <p>Total number of clusters (total): 20*</p> <p>Clusters in RDA arm: 10</p> <p>Total population in RDA arm: ~110,000</p> <p>Total population in control/comparison arm: ~110,000</p>
Participants	<p>Number of RDA 'events': Not available</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 65,319 over four rounds</p> <p>Percent of total targeted: N/A but estimated household coverage = 71.4% (95% CI: 66.7, 76.) across all four rounds</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RDA: Dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine</p> <p>Index case detection: Through active surveillance that took place during four "rounds": 1) December 2014, 2) Feb–March 2015, 3) October 2015, and 4) February 2016; all household members were tested with a <i>Pf</i> RDT and if anyone tested positive, the entire household was treated</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: Index case household only</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: No reactive treatment (enhanced intervention package only)</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> Scaled intervention package throughout trial areas included ITNs, IRS (2 rounds with Actellic in 2014 and 2015), enhanced malaria case management through expansion of CHW-based community case management, high-quality surveillance and reporting</p> <p><i>Note: 20 additional health facility clusters randomized to mass drug administration (MDA) but not included in this review.</i></p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Incidence of parasitemia:</u></p> <p>Cohort of targeted 2,250 individuals ≥ 3 months followed monthly (RDT and PCR)</p> <p>Analysis: Random-effects negative binomial regression model (with a random effect at individual and cluster level); adjusted model included PCR infection at baseline, age, gender, wealth quintile, household IRS at baseline, elevation, mean rainfall over study period, and mean environmental vegetation index over study period.</p> <p><u>Prevalence of parasitemia:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional household surveys</p> <p>Persons sampled: Children aged 3 to 70 months</p>

	<p>Diagnostic test used: RDT</p> <p>Time point(s): 3 surveys conducted: 1) Pre-intervention (April–May 2014), 2) Post-intervention 1 (April–May 2015, after treatment rounds 1 and 2), and 3) Post-intervention 2 (April–May 2016, after treatment rounds 3 and 4)</p> <p>Sample size (range): 304–521 (RDA), 332–505 (control)</p> <p>Analysis: Logistic regression with random effect for cluster; adjusted for child age, gender, household wealth, rainfall, enhanced vegetation index (EVI), household elevation, and household protection by LLINs and IRS.</p> <p><u>Incidence of clinical cases:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Routine data on malaria cases from community health workers and facilities accessed through DHIS2</p> <p>Time points: Jan 2012 – May 2016</p> <p>Analysis: Negative binomial difference-in-differences model with random effect for cluster; adjusted for monthly total rainfall, EVI, and previous month’s case counts.</p>
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Risk of bias

Bias	Authors’ judgement	Support for judgement
Randomization process	Low risk	Random allocation via computer algorithm
Recruitment of participants into clusters	Low risk	No serious baseline imbalances, coverage of RDA >70%
Deviations from intended interventions	Low risk	No evidence of deviations from intended intervention.
Missing outcome data (parasitemia incidence)	Low risk	Mean monthly follow-up similar across study arms, nearly 90% completed at least 12 months of follow-up.
Missing outcome data (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	Separate sampling done at each survey round; no evidence of high missingness.
Missing outcome data (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Based on routine reporting of data from facilities and community health workers in a well-established system with low missing data
Measurement of outcome (parasitemia incidence)	Low risk	PCR done in the lab and unlikely that laboratory scientists knew which cluster patients were from.
Measurement of outcome (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	Unlikely that study team differentially interpreted RDT results based on study cluster
Measurement of outcome (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Based on routine reporting of data from facilities and community health workers.

Selection of reported result (parasitemia incidence)	Low risk	Based on previously specified analysis plan.
Selection of reported result (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	Based on previously specified analysis plan.
Selection of reported result (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Based on previously specified analysis plan.

Hsiang 2020

Methods	<p>Location: Zambezi region, northern Namibia</p> <p>Study dates: January–December 2017</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: 32.5 per 1,000 in 2016 (previously <15 per 1,000 since 2010)</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial with factorial design: RDA, reactive vector control, both, and control</p> <p>Unit of randomization: Census enumeration area</p> <p>Total number of clusters (total): 56</p> <p>Clusters in RDA arm: 28 (14 also with reactive IRS)</p> <p>Total population in RDA arm: ~16,500 (total population in catchment areas = 33,418)</p> <p>Total population in control/comparison arm: ~16,500</p>
Participants	<p>Number of RDA 'events': 164 (from 492 eligible cases)</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 4,247</p> <p>Percent of total targeted: 86.7%</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RDA: Artemether-lumefantrine</p> <p>Index case detection: Through passive surveillance at 11 health facilities (total for the trial)</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: Households within a 500-meter radius, with a target up at least 25 individuals</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Reactive case detection with artemether-lumefantrine plus low-dose (0.25 mg/kg) primaquine targeting households within a 500-meter radius</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> Case management, annual IRS with DDT; R-IRS in half the clusters</p>

	<i>Note that half the RDA and half the reactive case detection clusters had reactive indoor residual spraying (R-IRS).</i>
Outcomes	<p><u>Prevalence of parasitemia:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional household survey</p> <p>Persons sampled: All household members</p> <p>Diagnostic test used: PCR</p> <p>Time point(s): May – August 2017</p> <p>Sample size: 1,932 (RDA), 2,150 (RACD)</p> <p>Analysis: Authors used a log binomial regression with a log link to estimate prevalence ratios using generalized estimating equations to adjust for enumeration area-level clustering. Models included terms for RDA, for reactive IRS, and the interaction between the two. Adjusted model also included 2016 incidence of local cases, index case level and target population coverage for RAD or RDA, response times, and co-interventions by the Ministry of Health.</p> <p><u>Incidence of clinical cases:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Routine data on malaria cases diagnosed by microscopy and RDT at health facilities</p> <p>Time points: Jan 2017 – December 2017</p> <p>Analysis: Negative binomial regression using a generalized linear model to estimate incidence rate ratios using cluster-level case data and cluster person-time as an offset. Models included terms for RDA, for reactive IRS, and the interaction between the two. Adjusted model also included 2016 incidence of local cases, index case level and target population coverage for RAD or RDA, response times, and co-interventions by the Ministry of Health. Note that cases and person-time counted starting only 8 weeks after the first intervention administered in each cluster.</p> <p><u>Adverse events:</u></p> <p>AEs were detected by having participants call an on-call study nurse and by follow-up visits by a study nurse among a portion of those receiving artermether-lumefantrine. In total 23 AEs in 18 individuals were reported, including headache (n=5), dizziness (n=5), diarrhea (n=3), vomiting (n=2), abdominal pain (n=2), fever (n=2), and weakness, cough, decreased appetite and muscle pain (1 each); 19 (83%) AEs were mild (grade 1) and four (17%) were moderate (grade 2). 17 (74%) of 23 adverse events were actively detected at follow-up visits. Six AEs were classified as probably related to treatment, 6 as possibly related, and 11 as unrelated. Of the 18 participants reporting at least one AE, 17 were in the RDA group and 1 in the RACD group.</p>

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Randomization process	Low risk	Computer-generated restricted randomization used
Recruitment of participants into clusters	Low risk	Unlikely to have been differential recruitment by arm; participation rates similar across arms
Deviations from intended interventions	Low risk	No evidence of wrong intervention or deviations due to trial context
Missing outcome data (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	Equal numbers of children per arm sampled; no evidence of differential missingness
Missing outcome data (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Based on routine data reported; no evidence of differential missingness
Missing outcome data (adverse events)	Some concerns	Unclear to what extent adverse events were captured in the RACD arm (although one adverse event reported from RACD arm).
Measurement of outcome (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	PCR done in the laboratory; unlikely that analysis affected by knowledge of study arm
Measurement of outcome (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Routine diagnosis at health facilities; unlikely that diagnosis affected by knowledge of study arm
Measurement of outcome (adverse events)	High risk	Likely that adverse event reporting was much stronger in RDA arm compared to reactive case detection arm.
Selection of reported result (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	Pre-stated outcome
Selection of reported result (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Pre-stated outcome
Selection of reported result (adverse events)	Low risk	Pre-stated outcome

Okebe 2021

Methods	<p>Location: The Gambia (North Bank East and Lower River health regions)</p> <p>Study dates: August 2017 – December 2018</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: Not available but malaria prevalence by molecular methods in 2012 was 4.6% and 9.4% in North Bank and Lower River regions, respectively.</p>
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	<p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial of RDA compared to RACD only for symptomatic household members of index case.</p> <p>Unit of randomization: Village</p> <p>Total number of clusters (total): 50 (16 villages added in November 2017 due to lower-than-anticipated malaria prevalence in the control arm)</p> <p>Clusters in RDA arm: 25 (7 added in year 2 of trial)</p> <p>Total population in RDA arm: 8,645</p> <p>Total population in control/comparison arm: 10,300</p>
Participants	<p>Number of RDA 'events': 71</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 979</p> <p>Percent of total targeted: 96.6%</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RDA: Dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine</p> <p>Index case detection: Passive detection by village health workers by RDT</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: Compound of index case (all residents)</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Reactive case detection with artemether-lumefantrine for symptomatic members of the index case compound who tested positive by RDT.</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> Not specified</p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Prevalence of parasitemia:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional survey (done twice, in 2017 and 2018) with finger-prick blood collection for PCR. The 2018 survey results were used for this review.</p> <p>Persons sampled: Random sample (proportional to village size) of residents of all ages</p> <p>Diagnostic test used: PCR</p> <p>Time point(s): 2017 and 2018</p> <p>Sample size: In 2018: 1,924 (RDA) and 1,824 (control)</p> <p>Analysis: Random effects logistic regression model; adjusted model included age.</p> <p><u>Incidence of clinical cases:</u></p>

	<p>Measurement: Routine data on malaria cases diagnosed by microscopy and RDT at health facilities</p> <p>Time points: Jan 2017 – December 2017</p> <p>Analysis: Random effects logistic regression model; adjusted model included age.</p> <p><u>Adverse events:</u></p> <p>Village health workers (who delivered the RDA) returned on day four to ask about adverse events; it is unclear if/how AEs were solicited in RACD arm. Total of 75 AEs among the 979 participants receiving dihydroartemisinin-piperazine: 11 (14.7%) vomiting, 10 (13.3%) loose stools, 7 (9.3%) diarrhea, 7 (9.3%) dizziness (7 (9.3%) nausea and the rest included body aches, abdominal pain headache, tiredness, weakness, and other. 69 AEs considered mild and 6 moderate.</p>
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Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Randomization process	Low risk	Computer-generated algorithm by trial statistician
Recruitment of participants into clusters	Low risk	Confirmed cases fully investigated in both RDA and RACD arms
Deviations from intended interventions	Low risk	High participation and adherence to treatment in RDA arm
Missing outcome data (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	No evidence of differential missingness by study arm
Missing outcome data (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Based on routine data reported; no evidence of differential missingness
Missing outcome data (adverse events)	High risk	Adverse events reported only from RDA arm
Measurement of outcome (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	Random sample of participants drawn from each village in each study arm
Measurement of outcome (clinical malaria incidence)	Some concerns	Routine diagnosis by village health workers who also delivered intervention; unlikely but possible that diagnosis affected by knowledge of study arm
Measurement of outcome (adverse events)	High risk	Active follow-up for adverse events only in RDA arm
Selection of reported result (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	Pre-specified outcome
Selection of reported result (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Pre-specified outcome
Selection of reported result (adverse events)	Low risk	Pre-specified outcome

Vilakati 2021

Methods	<p>Location: eastern malaria-endemic areas of Eswatini</p> <p>Study dates: September 2015 – August 2017</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: 5.2 per 1,000 from 2012–2015</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial comparing RDA to RACD</p> <p>Unit of randomization: Locality</p> <p>Total number of clusters (total): 77</p> <p>Clusters in RDA arm: 39</p> <p>Total population in RDA arm: 2,680 (note that the population only includes the 'at-risk' population (part of the enumeration area within the locality that had incident cases during the trial))</p> <p>Total population in RACD arm: 2,752</p>
Participants	<p>Number of RDA 'events': 64 (covering 76 cases in 25 localities)</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 1,776</p> <p>Percent of total targeted: 72.3%</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RDA: Dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine</p> <p>Index case detection: Through passive surveillance at health facilities and confirmed by RDT or microscopy</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: Households within a 200-meter radius of index case, targeting a minimum of 30 individuals</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Reactive case detection with artemether-lumefantrine targeting households within a 500-meter radius; those testing positive by RDT were referred to the nearest health facility for treatment.</p> <p>Note that RACD was routinely carried out by the Ministry of Health and this was continued in the RACD arm for this study.</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> Case management, pre-season IRS</p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Incidence of clinical cases:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Routine data on malaria cases diagnosed by microscopy and RDT at health facilities. Only local cases included in outcome (although the authors did an analysis with all cases as well).</p> <p>Time points: Jan 2017 – December 2017</p> <p>Analysis: Negative binomial regression with an offset for cluster population size. The first index case in each cluster was not included to allow time for the intervention to have an effect. Adjusted model included covariates</p>

	<p>associated with an outcome (not pre-specified), which was incidence of local cases in 2014 – 2015.</p> <p><u>Adverse events:</u></p> <p>AEs occurred in 68 individuals in the RDA arm, mostly headache, nausea/vomiting, and abdominal pain; 54 (80%) were mild and 14 (21%) were moderate. Counseling on AE reporting occurred during administration of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine to those receiving RDA; there was a study nurse on call 24 hours per day, 7 days per week and also active pharmacovigilance in the community. For those in the RACD arm referred to facilities to take AL, there was not systematic counseling on AE reporting.</p>
Notes	

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Randomization process	Some concerns	Baseline imbalances due to inclusion of only clusters with an index case
Recruitment of participants into clusters	Low risk	Similar participation rates in both arms of the trial
Deviations from intended interventions	Some concerns	20 RACD interventions delivered in RDA arm (14 clusters); 5 RDA interventions delivered in RACD arm
Missing outcome data (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	No reason to believe there was differential missingness by study arm
Missing outcome data (adverse events)	High risk	Adverse events reported only from RDA arm
Measurement of outcome (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Routine diagnosis at health facilities; unlikely that diagnosis affected by knowledge of study arm
Measurement of outcome (adverse events)	High risk	Adverse events reported only from RDA arm
Selection of reported result (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Pre-specified outcome
Selection of reported result (adverse events)	Low risk	Pre-specified outcome

Non-randomized studies

Quispe 2018

Methods	<p>Location: Tumbes region of Peru</p> <p>Study dates: 2009 (month unspecified) to 2010 (month unspecified)</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: 8.2 per 1,000 in 2010 (almost all <i>P. vivax</i>)</p>
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	<p>Study design: Non-randomized quasi-experimental study using weekly malaria incidence data</p> <p>Total population in RDA arm: 36,231 (2 districts)</p> <p>Total population in comparison area: 163,984 (8 districts)</p>
Participants	<p>Number of RDA 'events': 867</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 7,376</p> <p>Percent of total targeted: Not available</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RDA: CQ (25 mg/kg) for 72 hours plus PQ (0.5 mg/kg) for 7 days</p> <p>Index case detection: Through passive surveillance at health facilities and confirmed by microscopy</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: Only household members plus social contacts and excluding children <5, adults >65, pregnant women, chronically ill</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Routine passive case detection at health facilities; diagnosis by microscopy, and treatment with CQ (25 mg/kg) for 72 hours plus PQ (0.5 mg/kg) for 7 days for positive cases.</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> Not specified</p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Incidence of clinical cases:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Routine weekly data on malaria cases diagnosed by microscopy at health facilities.</p> <p>Time points: 2009 –2010</p> <p>Analysis: Mixed effects Poisson regression of weekly cases with variable for intervention district. Adjusted model included climate covariates associated with outcome, including pressure, humidity, temperature, moisture, precipitation , and vegetation.</p> <p><u>Adverse events:</u></p> <p>None reported from any of the 13 districts (2 study plus 11 comparison) in the study.</p>

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Application of appropriate eligibility criteria	Some concerns	The two intervention districts had substantially higher malaria transmission

		at baseline than those included in the control
Flawed measurement in the exposure (i.e. intervention)	Some concerns	No information on the proportion of cases that were followed up with RDA
Flawed measurement in the outcome	Some concerns	No information was provided on the coverage of health systems in the intervention and control communities
Failure to adequately control for confounding	Some concerns	Differences in baseline risk between intervention and comparison districts do not seem to be accounted for in the analysis model.
Incomplete follow-up (loss that could introduce bias)	Low risk	No reason to expect that there was loss to follow up as the indicator for malaria incidence is at the cluster level.
Downgrade from low to very low?	Yes	

References

1. Cotter C, Sturrock HJ, Hsiang MS, Liu J, Phillips AA, Hwang J, et al. The changing epidemiology of malaria elimination: new strategies for new challenges. *Lancet*. 2013;382(9895):900-11.
2. Stresman G, Whittaker C, Slater HC, Bousema T, Cook J. Quantifying Plasmodium falciparum infections clustering within households to inform household-based intervention strategies for malaria control programs: An observational study and meta-analysis from 41 malaria-endemic countries. *PLoS Med*. 2020;17(10):e1003370.
3. Stuck L, Fakih BS, Al-Mafazy AH, Hofmann NE, Holzschuh A, Grossenbacher B, et al. Malaria infection prevalence and sensitivity of reactive case detection in Zanzibar. *Int J Infect Dis*. 2020;97:337-46.
4. Kobayashi T, Kanyangarara M, Laban NM, Phiri M, Hamapumbu H, Searle KM, et al. Characteristics of Subpatent Malaria in a Pre-Elimination Setting in Southern Zambia. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2019;100(2):280-6.
5. Bridges DJ, Miller JM, Chalwe V, Moonga H, Hamainza B, Steketee R, et al. Community-led Responses for Elimination (CoRE): a study protocol for a community randomized controlled trial assessing the effectiveness of community-level, reactive focal drug administration for reducing Plasmodium falciparum infection prevalence and incidence in Southern Province, Zambia. *Trials*. 2017;18(1):511.
6. Gerardin J, Bever CA, Hamainza B, Miller JM, Eckhoff PA, Wenger EA. Optimal Population-Level Infection Detection Strategies for Malaria Control and Elimination in a Spatial Model of Malaria Transmission. *PLoS Comput Biol*. 2016;12(1):e1004707.
7. Okebe J, Ribera JM, Balen J, Jaiteh F, Masunaga Y, Nwakanma D, et al. Reactive community-based self-administered treatment against residual malaria transmission: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial. *Trials*. 2018;19(1):126.
8. Baltzell KA, Maglior A, Bangu K, Mngadi N, Prach LM, Whittemore B, et al. "We were afraid of the lion that has roared next to us"; community response to reactive focal mass drug administration for malaria in Eswatini (formerly Swaziland). *Malar J*. 2019;18(1):238.
9. Hsiang MS, Ntuku H, Roberts KW, Dufour MK, Whittemore B, Tambo M, et al. Effectiveness of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control to reduce malaria transmission in the low malaria-endemic setting of Namibia: a cluster-randomised controlled, open-label, two-by-two factorial design trial. *Lancet*. 2020;395(10233):1361-73.
10. Eisele TP, Silumbe K, Finn T, Chalwe V, Kamuliwo M, Hamainza B, et al. Assessing the effectiveness of household-level focal mass drug administration and community-wide mass drug administration for reducing malaria parasite infection prevalence and

incidence in Southern Province, Zambia: study protocol for a community randomized controlled trial. *Trials*. 2015;16:347.

11. Sterne JAC, Savovic J, Page MJ, Elbers RG, Blencowe NS, Boutron I, et al. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ*. 2019;366:l4898.
12. Higgins J, Savovic J, Page MJ, Elbers RG, Sterne J. Assessing risk of bias in a randomized trial. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* Cochrane; 2020.
13. Guyatt GH, Oxman AD, Vist G, Kunz R, Brozek J, Alonso-Coello P, et al. GRADE guidelines: 4. Rating the quality of evidence--study limitations (risk of bias). *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):407-15.
14. Guyatt G, Oxman AD, Akl EA, Kunz R, Vist G, Brozek J, et al. GRADE guidelines: 1. Introduction-GRADE evidence profiles and summary of findings tables. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):383-94.
15. Balshem H, Helfand M, Schunemann HJ, Oxman AD, Kunz R, Brozek J, et al. GRADE guidelines: 3. Rating the quality of evidence. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):401-6.
16. Quispe A. Challenges and opportunities for pursuing malaria elimination in Peru. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University; 2018.
17. Gerardin J, Bever CA, Hamainza B, Miller JM, Eckhoff PA, Wenger EA. Optimal Population-Level Infection Detection Strategies for Malaria Control and Elimination in a Spatial Model of Malaria Transmission. *PLoS Computational Biology*. 2016;12(1):e1004707.
18. Eisele TP, Bennett A, Silumbe K, Finn TP, Porter TR, Chalwe V, et al. Impact of Four Rounds of Mass Drug Administration with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine Implemented in Southern Province, Zambia. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine & Hygiene*. 2020;103(2_Suppl):7-18.
19. Okebe J, Dabira E, Jaiteh F, Mohammed N, Bradley J, Drammeh NF, et al. Reactive, self-administered malaria treatment against asymptomatic malaria infection: results of a cluster randomized controlled trial in The Gambia. *Malar J*. 2021;20(1):253.
20. Bridges D, Miller J, Chalwa V, Moonga H, Hamainza B, Steketee R, et al. Serological evaluations of malaria in the cluster randomized community-led responses for elimination (CoRE) trial. [Not yet published]2021.
21. Vilakati S, Mngadi N, Benjamin-Chung J, Dlamini N, Dufour MK, Whittemore B, et al. Effectiveness and safety of reactive focal mass drug administration (rfMDA) using dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine to reduce malaria transmission in the very low-endemic setting of Eswatini: a pragmatic cluster randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2021;6(6).
22. Hsiang MS, Ntshalintshali N, Kang Dufour MS, Dlamini N, Nhlabathi N, Vilakati S, et al. Active Case Finding for Malaria: A 3-Year National Evaluation of Optimal Approaches

- to Detect Infections and Hotspots Through Reactive Case Detection in the Low-transmission Setting of Eswatini. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2020;70(7):1316-25.
23. Yukich JO, Scott C, Kafula S, Larson BA, Bennett A, Finn TP, et al. Cost-effectiveness of focal mass drug administration and mass drug administration with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine for malaria prevention in Southern Province, Zambia: results of a community-randomized controlled trial. (Special Issue: Mass drug administration for malaria: the Zambia southern province trial.). *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2020;103(2 Suppl):46-53.
24. Finn TP, Yukich JO, Bennett A, Porter TR, Lungu C, Hamainza B, et al. Treatment coverage estimation for mass drug administration for malaria with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine in Southern Province, Zambia. (Special Issue: Mass drug administration for malaria: the Zambia southern province trial.). *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2020;103(2 Suppl):19-27.
25. Silumbe K, Finn TP, Jennings T, Sikombe C, Chiyende E, Hamainza B, et al. Assessment of the Acceptability of Testing and Treatment during a Mass Drug Administration Trial for Malaria in Zambia Using Mixed Methods. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine & Hygiene*. 2020;103(2_Suppl):28-36.
26. Roberts KW, Smith Gueye C, Baltzell K, Ntuku H, McCreesh P, Maglior A, et al. Community acceptance of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control using indoor residual spraying, a mixed-methods study in Zambezi region, Namibia. *Malar J*. 2021;20(1):162.
27. Jaiteh F, Masunaga Y, Okebe J, D'Alessandro U, Balen J, Bradley J, et al. Community perspectives on treating asymptomatic infections for malaria elimination in The Gambia. *Malar J*. 2019;18(1):39.
28. Finn TP, Porter TR, Moonga H, Silumbe K, Daniels RF, Volkman SK, et al. Adherence to Mass Drug Administration with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine and *Plasmodium falciparum* Clearance in Southern Province, Zambia. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine & Hygiene*. 2020;103(2_Suppl):37-45.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Definitions of outcomes and contextual factors

- 1) Incidence of malaria infection
- 2) Prevalence of malaria infection
- 3) Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the peak transmission season)
- 4) Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases

Measured among those targeted by the intervention

- 5) Adverse events
- 6) Prevalence of infection

OUTCOMES	
<i>Measured at community level</i>	
1) Incidence of malaria infection	Number of cases of malaria identified through active surveillance, divided by the product of the population and the time under observation
2) Prevalence of malaria infection	Number of people with malaria parasitemia (diagnostically confirmed) divided by the number tested, among a given population
3) Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the peak transmission season)	Zero measured indigenous or local cases for a period during the peak transmission season
4) Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases	Number of local (indigenous) malaria cases among a certain population over a given time period; if measured by passive case detection, typically expressed as the number of cases divided by the population (for the time period specified); if measured in an incidence cohort, typically expressed as the number of cases divided by person-time
<i>Among those receiving the intervention</i>	
5) Adverse events	Known adverse drug events for the given antimalarial medication used
6) Prevalence of infection	Number of people with malaria parasitemia (diagnostically confirmed) divided by the number tested, among the population (or a subset) receiving reactive drug administration
CONTEXTUAL FACTORS	
Values and preferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The values and preferences of the individuals and populations affected by the recommendation with respect to the outcomes associated with the intervention

Acceptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent to which those benefiting from the intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate (based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention) • Willingness to participate in the intervention
Health equity, equality and non-discrimination	<p>Extent to which the intervention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits all populations • Does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence or any other characteristic. • <i>Note:</i> This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all
Financial and economic considerations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs • Resource intensiveness • Overall economic impact • Cost-benefit
Feasibility and health system considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal barriers to implementation • Interaction with existing health system • Need for and use of the existing health workforce (e.g., to conduct intervention) or other resources • Programmatic considerations • <i>Note:</i> this includes the ability to reach all targeted households/household members in a timely manner; adherence to drug completion among those given antimalarials

Appendix 2: Search terms and results

Search Query: Reactive strategies include either: reactive case detection (testing and treating those positive) around an index case (presenting to health facilities or community health workers), drug administration (without testing) for households around an index case

Search Strategy:

Database	Strategy	Run Date	Records
Medline (OVID) 1946-	Malaria* AND (((screen* ADJ5 treat*) OR (test* ADJ5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (passive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 administration) OR (reactive* ADJ5 screen*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 test*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 treat*) OR (focal ADJ5 administration) OR (foci ADJ5 administration) OR (focal ADJ5 MDA) OR (foci ADJ5 MDA)	11/16/2020	416
Embase (OVID) 1988-	Malaria* AND (((screen* ADJ5 treat*) OR (test* ADJ5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (passive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 administration) OR (reactive* ADJ5 screen*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 test*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 treat*) OR (focal ADJ5 administration) OR (foci ADJ5 administration) OR (focal ADJ5 MDA) OR (foci ADJ5 MDA) NOT pubmed/medline	11/16/2020	715 -387 duplicates =328 unique items
Global Health (OVID) 1910_	Malaria* AND (((screen* ADJ5 treat*) OR (test* ADJ5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (passive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 administration) OR (reactive* ADJ5 screen*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 test*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 treat*) OR (focal ADJ5 administration) OR (foci ADJ5 administration) OR (focal ADJ5 MDA) OR (foci ADJ5 MDA)	11/16/2020	451 -334 duplicates =117 unique items
Cochrane Library	Malaria*:ti,ab AND ((((screen* NEAR/5 treat*) OR (test* NEAR/5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 detect*) OR (passive* NEAR/5 detect*) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 administration) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 screen*) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 test*) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 treat*) OR (focal NEAR/5 administration) OR	11/16/2020	161 -105 duplicates =56 unique items

	(foci NEAR/5 administration) OR (focal NEAR/5 MDA) OR (foci NEAR/5 MDA):ti,ab		
CINAHL (EbscoHost)	Malaria* AND (((screen* N5 treat*) OR (test* N5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* N5 detect*) OR (passive* N5 detect*) OR (reactive* N5 administration) OR (reactive* N5 screen*) OR (reactive* N5 test*) OR (reactive* N5 treat*) OR (focal N5 administration) OR (foci N5 administration) OR (focal N5 MDA) OR (foci N5 MDA))	11/16/2020	75 -57 duplicates =18 unique items
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY(Malaria*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY((((screen* W/5 treat*) OR (test* W/5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* W/5 detect*) OR (passive* W/5 detect*) OR (reactive* W/5 administration) OR (reactive* W/5 screen*) OR (reactive* W/5 test*) OR (reactive* W/5 treat*) OR (focal W/5 administration) OR (foci W/5 administration) OR (focal W/5 MDA) OR (foci W/5 MDA))	11/16/2020	552 -445 duplicates =107 unique items
Clinicaltrials.gov	Malaria reactive case detection completed OR focal mass drug administration OR foci mass drug administration OR focal MDA OR foci MDA Completed Studies malaria	11/16/2020	6 -1 duplicates =5 unique items
Global Index Medicus	Malaria* AND ((screen* OR test*) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* AND detect*) OR (passive* AND detect*) OR (reactive* AND administration) OR (reactive* AND screen*) OR (reactive* AND test*) OR (reactive* AND treat*) OR (focal AND administration) OR (foci AND administration) OR (focal AND MDA) OR (foci AND MDA)	11/16/2020	313 -36 duplicates =277 unique items

Notes: Duplicates were identified using the Endnote automated "find duplicates" function with preference set to match on title, author and year, and removed from your Endnote library. There will likely be additional duplicates found that Endnote was unable to detect.

Appendix 3: Alternative forest plots for prevalence of parasitemia and incidence of confirmed malaria (with correct lower bound for 95% CI for Hsiang 2020(9))

Figure 10: Forest plot of comparison: RDA versus no RDA/RACD on parasitemia prevalence, using correct lower bound for Hsiang 2020 95% confidence interval

Footnotes

- (2) and (2) Random effects logistic regression model adjusted for child age (in years), gender, household wealth from an asset index, rainfall, enhanced vegetation index, household elevation, and household protection by LLINs and IRS.
- (5) The 95% CI upper limit is higher here than in the published paper (odds ratio = 0.54, 95% CI: 0.05, 1.04). Effect size from (non-linear) marginal effect post-estimation from generalized estimating equations (GEE) model using a logit function and including variables for RDA, reactive IRS, the interaction between reactive IRS and RDA, and adjusted for 2016 incidence of local cases. Unadjusted effect size (from post-estimation marginal effect of RDA from GEE model using a logit function with variables for RDA, reactive IRS, the interaction between reactive IRS and RDA but no other covariates): 1.05 (0.03, 2.07).
- (6) Random effects logistic regression (random effect for health facility) adjusted for age. Unadjusted odds ratio: 0.73 (95% CI: 0.27, 1.94).

Figure 11 Forest plot of comparison: RDA versus no RDA/RACD on confirmed malaria incidence, using correct lower bound for Hsiang 2020 95% confidence interval

Footnotes

- (1) Negative binomial analysis of monthly facility cases (random intercept for facility); adjusted for previous month's cases, normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), precipitation, altitude, night-time light, number RDTs done each month, and seasonality (fourier term). Unadjusted estimate: 1.08 (95% CI: 0.78, 1.49).
- (2) and (3) Negative binomial difference-in-differences model (one pre- and one post time point), adjusted for prior month's cases, calendar month, rainfall, and EVI monthly anomalies.
- (4) The 95% CI upper limit is higher here than in the published paper (rate ratio=0.71 (05% CI: 0.22, **1.20**). Effect size from (non-linear) marginal effect post-estimation from a negative binomial model with offset for cluster-level person time;

variables for RDA, reactive vector control, interaction between RDA and reactive vector control, and adjusted for 2016 incidence of local cases. Unadjusted marginal effects from post-estimation (from unadjusted negative binomial model with variables for RDA, reactive IRS, and the interaction between the two, with offset for cluster-level person time): 0.82 (0.26, 1.37).

- (5) Poisson regression model adjusted for age. Unadjusted estimate from a logistic regression model (with a random effect for cluster): 1.04 (95% CI: 0.57, 1.91).
- (6) Negative binomial regression model of local cases with offset for person-time and adjusted for baseline (2014-2015) incidence of local cases. Unadjusted estimate: 1.06 (95% CI: 0.57, 1.98).

Introduction

The extent to which systematic reviews and guidelines of complex interventions, like reactive drug administration (RDA), consider and report contextual factors that determine the direction and strength of a recommendation in public health policy formulations(29) is limited by inadequate information on context in included primary studies(30). To facilitate a structured process of reflection and discussion in a problem-specific and context-specific manner, the WHO in its new WHO-INTEGRATE (INTEGRATE Evidence) evidence to decision framework 1.0, recommends reporting and consideration of six substantive criteria—balance of health benefits and harms, human rights and sociocultural acceptability, health equity, equality and non-discrimination, societal implications, financial and economic considerations, and feasibility and health system considerations—and the meta-criterion quality of evidence, applicable to all the six criteria. The first criteria balance of health benefits and harms was the primary objective of our systematic reviews and is reported in the main body of this report (Page XX) . In this study, we report on contextual factors that align with these criteria and are relevant for RDA guideline development process.

Ten studies from sub-Saharan Africa were reviewed for contextual factors (Table 1). Data was not available for the following two categories of contextual factors: values and preferences, and health equity. We abstracted data for the other three categories of contextual factors which are discussed below.

Acceptability

RDA community acceptability data were abstracted from 6 studies from Eswatini(8), The Gambia(19, 27), Namibia(9, 26), Zambia(31). Community acceptance of RDA was high (refusal rate of 2% or lower) in Namibia (Table 2). However, in Eswatini, the overall refusal rate was about 4% with refusal rate of 1.4% (11/776) and 5.3% (65/1232) in seasons 1 and 2, respectively. In Zambia, there was a large increase in self-reported acceptability of prophylactic treatment if negative for malaria from the baseline to follow-up survey for adults and children, from 62% to 96%(31). Intensive community-wide sensitization program that occurred before the first treatment round at each household during community health worker visits is reported to have resulted in this increase. Despite low refusal rate, numerous stigmas associated (Table 3) with malaria RDT, CHWs, and treatment were reported in some of these countries(26, 31). In Zambia, participants were concerned “whether CHWs or the program was tenets of Satanism” and said, “this medicine you have brought is Satanic”. In Namibia, participants expressed concern about having “to take medicine without feeling sick”, similarly participants in The

Gambia “generally considered it unnecessary to take medication without having any symptoms” (27). Continued community sensitization has been recommended to mitigate these stigmas.

In our review, we found no study reporting on health care workers’ or policymakers’ acceptability of RDA.

Feasibility

Data on feasibility of implementing RDA were abstracted from 5 studies from Eswatini(21), The Gambia(19), Namibia(9) and Zambia(32, 33). All countries used a three-day regimen of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DHAp) for RDA. RDA coverage, defined as proportion of index cases followed up, varied between countries (Table 4) with a low of 62.4% for index case coverage in Eswatini to about 97% in The Gambia.

RDA adherence data were abstracted from 3 studies from Eswatini(8), The Gambia(19), and Zambia(32). Full adherence, defined as taking all three doses of DHAp and verifying that no tablets were remaining in the blister pack was above 90% (Table 4) in all the countries. DHAp was generally reported to be well tolerated with mild to moderate self-limiting side effects. However, a study from Zambia reported that 5% of patients receiving DHAp stopped treatment early due to unspecified side effects(32). In Zambia(32), factors positively related to DHAp adherence were RDT positivity, age >15 (versus <5 years), receiving the first dose as directly observed therapy (DOT) by the community health worker (CHW), and hearing sensitization messages. One factor negatively related to adherence was fever in last 2 weeks. In a study from Namibia(26), respondents anticipated reluctance about completing the full course DHAp, explaining that some people might stop once symptoms diminished, or if symptoms did not subside immediately. Respondents also reported that “people may save medication to treat future illness, given limited access and distance from health facilities.(26)”

Financial and economic costs

In a study conducted in Zambia, RDA does not appear likely to achieve WHO thresholds for being considered a “cost-effective” or “highly cost-effective” intervention(34). The total cost of two rounds of RDA (with DHAp) conducted between 2014 and 2015 in seven treatment arms with a total population of 132,393 was US\$ 912,767 (all figures in 2015 US\$). The mean cost per person treated per health facility catchment area was \$85.69 (interquartile range, \$39.92). The overall incremental cost (vs. standard of care) per infection and case averted for RDA was \$810 and \$6,353, respectively. In high transmission settings, the incremental cost per infection and case averted were \$429 and \$5,951 respectively; and in low transmission settings it was \$1,119 and \$6,755, respectively. Incremental cost per disability-adjusted life years averted for infections and cases were \$4,889 and \$38,344 respectively.

Results of this study show similar costs of RDA and mass drug administration (MDA) per person targeted and reached (US\$9.01 versus US\$8.49 per person, respectively, $P = 0.87$). However, MDA was reported to be superior in all cost-effectiveness measures, including cost per infection averted (\$ 354 for MDA vs. \$810 for RDA), cost per case averted (\$1,872 vs. \$6,353) and cost per disability-adjusted life year averted for infections (\$2,137 vs. \$4,889) and cases (\$11,299 vs. \$38,344).

Table 5 Studies included for RDA contextual factor data abstraction

Country	Title	Lead Author Year	Acceptability	Feasibility	Cost
The Gambia	Reactive, self-administered malaria treatment against asymptomatic malaria infection: results of a cluster randomized trial in The Gambia	Okebe, 2021	Y	Y	N
Namibia	Effectiveness of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control to reduce malaria transmission in the low malaria-endemic setting of Namibia: a cluster-randomised controlled, open-label, two-by-two factorial design trial	Hsiang 2020	Y	Y	N
Eswatini	Effectiveness and safety of reactive focal mass drug administration (rfMDA) using dihydroartemisinin-piperazine to reduce malaria transmission in very low-endemic setting of Eswatini: a pragmatic cluster randomised controlled trial	Vilakati 2021	N	Y	N
The Gambia	Community perspectives on treating asymptomatic infections for malaria elimination in The Gambia	Jaiteh 2019	Y	N	N
Namibia	Community acceptance of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control using indoor residual spraying, a mixed-methods study in Zambezi region, Namibia	Roberts 2021	Y	N	N
Zambia	Treatment coverage estimation for mass drug administration for malaria with dihydroartemisinin-piperazine in Southern Province, Zambia.	Finn 2020	N	Y	N
Zambia	Cost-effectiveness of focal mass drug administration and mass drug administration with dihydroartemisinin-piperazine for malaria prevention in Southern Province, Zambia: results of a community-randomized controlled trial.	Yukich 2020	N	N	Y
Zambia	Adherence to Mass Drug Administration with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperazine and Plasmodium falciparum Clearance in Southern Province, Zambia	Finn 2020	N	Y	N
Zambia	Assessment of the Acceptability of Testing and Treatment during a Mass Drug Administration Trial for Malaria in Zambia Using Mixed Methods	Silumbe 2020	Y	N	N

Eswatini	"We were afraid of the lion that has roared next to us"; community response to reactive focal mass drug administration for malaria in Eswatini (formerly Swaziland)	Baltzell 2019	Y	N	N
Total			6	5	1

Table 6 RDA refusal rate

Country	Percentage refusing RDA	Round 1	Round 2
Eswatini(19)	3.8% (76/2008)	1.4% (11/776)	5.3% (65/1232)
Namibia(26)	0.93% (44/4716)	1.7% (8/478)	0.84% (36/4283)
Namibia(9)	0.66% (16/2407)	NA	NA

Table 7 Perceptions and concerns of participants on malaria RDT, CHWs and antimalarial drugs

Country	Malaria RDT	CHWs	Drugs (DHAp)
Zambia(31)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blood would be used for HIV diagnosis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concerns whether CHWs or the program was tenets of Satanism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “this medicine you have brought is Satanic. Others would say they are ARVs [antiretroviral]”
Namibia (26)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Association between HIV tests have similar appearance to malaria RDT Other would perceive them as “unclean” if family member had malaria” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None reported 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not wanting to take medicine without feeling sick

Table 8. Adherence to reactive drug administration

	RDA coverage	Full adherence	Drug regimen	Adverse events
Eswatini(8)	62.4%	99.3% (n = 1099)	DHAp 3 days	Mild
The Gambia(19)	96.6%	98.5% (964/979)	DHAp 3 days	Mild to moderate
Zambia(32)		92.8% overall (32,669/35,190) across four rounds, ranging from 91.5% to 95.6%	DHAp 3 days	5% stopped treatment early due to unspecified side effects (data for both MDA and RDA)

References:

1. Cotter C, Sturrock HJ, Hsiang MS, Liu J, Phillips AA, Hwang J, et al. The changing epidemiology of malaria elimination: new strategies for new challenges. *Lancet*. 2013;382(9895):900-11.
2. Stresman G, Whittaker C, Slater HC, Bousema T, Cook J. Quantifying Plasmodium falciparum infections clustering within households to inform household-based intervention strategies for malaria control programs: An observational study and meta-analysis from 41 malaria-endemic countries. *PLoS Med*. 2020;17(10):e1003370.
3. Stuck L, Fasih BS, Al-Mafazy AH, Hofmann NE, Holzschuh A, Grossenbacher B, et al. Malaria infection prevalence and sensitivity of reactive case detection in Zanzibar. *Int J Infect Dis*. 2020;97:337-46.
4. Kobayashi T, Kanyangarara M, Laban NM, Phiri M, Hamapumbu H, Searle KM, et al. Characteristics of Subpatent Malaria in a Pre-Elimination Setting in Southern Zambia. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2019;100(2):280-6.
5. Bridges DJ, Miller JM, Chalwe V, Moonga H, Hamainza B, Steketee R, et al. Community-led Responses for Elimination (CoRE): a study protocol for a community randomized controlled trial assessing the effectiveness of community-level, reactive focal drug administration for reducing Plasmodium falciparum infection prevalence and incidence in Southern Province, Zambia. *Trials*. 2017;18(1):511.
6. Gerardin J, Bever CA, Hamainza B, Miller JM, Eckhoff PA, Wenger EA. Optimal Population-Level Infection Detection Strategies for Malaria Control and Elimination in a Spatial Model of Malaria Transmission. *PLoS Comput Biol*. 2016;12(1):e1004707.
7. Okebe J, Ribera JM, Balen J, Jaiteh F, Masunaga Y, Nwakanma D, et al. Reactive community-based self-administered treatment against residual malaria transmission: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial. *Trials*. 2018;19(1):126.
8. Baltzell KA, Maglior A, Bangu K, Mngadi N, Prach LM, Whittemore B, et al. "We were afraid of the lion that has roared next to us"; community response to reactive focal mass drug administration for malaria in Eswatini (formerly Swaziland). *Malar J*. 2019;18(1):238.
9. Hsiang MS, Ntuku H, Roberts KW, Dufour MK, Whittemore B, Tambo M, et al. Effectiveness of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control to reduce malaria transmission in the low malaria-endemic setting of Namibia: a cluster-randomised controlled, open-label, two-by-two factorial design trial. *Lancet*. 2020;395(10233):1361-73.
10. Eisele TP, Silumbe K, Finn T, Chalwe V, Kamuliwo M, Hamainza B, et al. Assessing the effectiveness of household-level focal mass drug administration and community-wide mass drug administration for reducing malaria parasite infection prevalence and

incidence in Southern Province, Zambia: study protocol for a community randomized controlled trial. *Trials*. 2015;16:347.

11. Sterne JAC, Savovic J, Page MJ, Elbers RG, Blencowe NS, Boutron I, et al. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ*. 2019;366:l4898.
12. Higgins J, Savovic J, Page MJ, Elbers RG, Sterne J. Assessing risk of bias in a randomized trial. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* Cochrane; 2020.
13. Guyatt GH, Oxman AD, Vist G, Kunz R, Brozek J, Alonso-Coello P, et al. GRADE guidelines: 4. Rating the quality of evidence--study limitations (risk of bias). *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):407-15.
14. Guyatt G, Oxman AD, Akl EA, Kunz R, Vist G, Brozek J, et al. GRADE guidelines: 1. Introduction-GRADE evidence profiles and summary of findings tables. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):383-94.
15. Balshem H, Helfand M, Schunemann HJ, Oxman AD, Kunz R, Brozek J, et al. GRADE guidelines: 3. Rating the quality of evidence. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):401-6.
16. Quispe A. Challenges and opportunities for pursuing malaria elimination in Peru. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University; 2018.
17. Gerardin J, Bever CA, Hamainza B, Miller JM, Eckhoff PA, Wenger EA. Optimal Population-Level Infection Detection Strategies for Malaria Control and Elimination in a Spatial Model of Malaria Transmission. *PLoS Computational Biology*. 2016;12(1):e1004707.
18. Eisele TP, Bennett A, Silumbe K, Finn TP, Porter TR, Chalwe V, et al. Impact of Four Rounds of Mass Drug Administration with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine Implemented in Southern Province, Zambia. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine & Hygiene*. 2020;103(2_Suppl):7-18.
19. Okebe J, Dabira E, Jaiteh F, Mohammed N, Bradley J, Drammeh NF, et al. Reactive, self-administered malaria treatment against asymptomatic malaria infection: results of a cluster randomized controlled trial in The Gambia. *Malar J*. 2021;20(1):253.
20. Bridges D, Miller J, Chalwa V, Moonga H, Hamainza B, Steketee R, et al. Serological evaluations of malaria in the cluster randomized community-led responses for elimination (CoRE) trial. [Not yet published]2021.
21. Vilakati S, Mngadi N, Benjamin-Chung J, Dlamini N, Dufour MK, Whittemore B, et al. Effectiveness and safety of reactive focal mass drug administration (rfMDA) using dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine to reduce malaria transmission in the very low-endemic setting of Eswatini: a pragmatic cluster randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2021;6(6).
22. Hsiang MS, Ntshalintshali N, Kang Dufour MS, Dlamini N, Nhlabathi N, Vilakati S, et al. Active Case Finding for Malaria: A 3-Year National Evaluation of Optimal Approaches

- to Detect Infections and Hotspots Through Reactive Case Detection in the Low-transmission Setting of Eswatini. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2020;70(7):1316-25.
23. Yukich JO, Scott C, Kafula S, Larson BA, Bennett A, Finn TP, et al. Cost-effectiveness of focal mass drug administration and mass drug administration with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine for malaria prevention in Southern Province, Zambia: results of a community-randomized controlled trial. (Special Issue: Mass drug administration for malaria: the Zambia southern province trial.). *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2020;103(2 Suppl):46-53.
24. Finn TP, Yukich JO, Bennett A, Porter TR, Lungu C, Hamainza B, et al. Treatment coverage estimation for mass drug administration for malaria with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine in Southern Province, Zambia. (Special Issue: Mass drug administration for malaria: the Zambia southern province trial.). *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2020;103(2 Suppl):19-27.
25. Silumbe K, Finn TP, Jennings T, Sikombe C, Chiyende E, Hamainza B, et al. Assessment of the Acceptability of Testing and Treatment during a Mass Drug Administration Trial for Malaria in Zambia Using Mixed Methods. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine & Hygiene*. 2020;103(2_Suppl):28-36.
26. Roberts KW, Smith Gueye C, Baltzell K, Ntuku H, McCreesh P, Maglior A, et al. Community acceptance of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control using indoor residual spraying, a mixed-methods study in Zambezi region, Namibia. *Malar J*. 2021;20(1):162.
27. Jaiteh F, Masunaga Y, Okebe J, D'Alessandro U, Balen J, Bradley J, et al. Community perspectives on treating asymptomatic infections for malaria elimination in The Gambia. *Malar J*. 2019;18(1):39.
28. Finn TP, Porter TR, Moonga H, Silumbe K, Daniels RF, Volkman SK, et al. Adherence to Mass Drug Administration with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine and *Plasmodium falciparum* Clearance in Southern Province, Zambia. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine & Hygiene*. 2020;103(2_Suppl):37-45.
29. WHO handbook for guideline development 2014. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/145714>.
30. Booth A, Moore G, Flemming K, Garside R, Rollins N, Tuncalp O, et al. Taking account of context in systematic reviews and guidelines considering a complexity perspective. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2019;4(Suppl 1):e000840.
31. Silumbe K, Finn TP, Jennings T, Sikombe C, Chiyende E, Hamainza B, et al. Assessment of the Acceptability of Testing and Treatment during a Mass Drug Administration Trial for Malaria in Zambia Using Mixed Methods. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2020;103(2_Suppl):28-36.
32. Finn TP, Porter TR, Moonga H, Silumbe K, Daniels RF, Volkman SK, et al. Adherence to Mass Drug Administration with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine and *Plasmodium*

falciparum Clearance in Southern Province, Zambia. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2020;103(2_Suppl):37-45.

33. Finn TP, Yukich JO, Bennett A, Porter TR, Lungu C, Hamainza B, et al. Treatment Coverage Estimation for Mass Drug Administration for Malaria with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine in Southern Province, Zambia. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2020;103(2_Suppl):19-27.

34. Yukich JO, Scott C, Silumbe K, Larson BA, Bennett A, Finn TP, et al. Cost-Effectiveness of Focal Mass Drug Administration and Mass Drug Administration with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine for Malaria Prevention in Southern Province, Zambia: Results of a Community-Randomized Controlled Trial. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2020;103(2_Suppl):46-53.